

Optimizing AI-Integrated Creative Process in Advertising Industry through KBPMS Approach

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ABSTRACT

Background - The demand for content across various rising digital media platforms pushes the advertising sector to adopt Artificial Intelligence (AI) automation to improve creativity, speed, and efficiency, especially in areas like art direction, copywriting, and graphic design. While AI offers solutions to improve efficiency and support creative processes, advertising agency stakeholders start to see the urgency in assessing how AI can work alongside human creativity to produce essential quality content for the client's value creation as the industry moves forward for a sustainable business growth.

Methodology - This research uses mixed-method; Quantitative method to measure AI integration within advertising agencies and assess audience reactions to AI-generated ads, establishing a link between AI usage and audience behavior; Qualitative method through In-Depth Interviews to identify the underlying insights from the advertising professionals' perspective in integrating AI on daily basis. The findings are processed for the development of a Performance Management System (PMS) using AHP scored by industry experts as the basis to prioritize the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Practical implications – This PMS framework is designed for macro-level advertising agencies to monitor and optimize the use of AI tools effectively through weighted KPIs and strategic AI investments.

Originality/value – This study contributes to the existing industry study by introducing a performance measurement and addresses a theoretical gap between AI-driven creative process and its impact to the industry's value creation.

KEYWORDS: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Advertising Industry, Creative Process, Performance Management System (PMS).

I. INTRODUCTION

In 2023, the advertising and media sector dominated the market, accounting for more than 19.5% of worldwide AI revenue as illustrated in Figure 1. This prominence is due to the rapid expansion of marketing applications for AI, which attracted considerable interest during the (Kulik, 2023).

Figure 1. Global A Market (Neurosys, 2023)

Dansa Kreatif as one of the 5 biggest advertising industry in Indonesia, experiences a significant shift in its daily operations regarding to AI penetrating the employees' way of working. Specifically in the internal core process; Strategic Planners, Creatives, and Internal

Production House. The future organization plan is to also inject a new role of Prompt Engineer as a new specialization in maximizing internal AI utilization. However, advertising professionals, known for their high creative standards and commitment to evoking human emotions through their creative ideations and executions, frequently debate whether AI can truly match the quality of human-generated content. This concern is due to no tangible assessment in monitoring the quality of AI-generated creative outputs.

This research aims to answer two research questions:

- How do AI automation affect both the productivity and quality of creative process within advertising agencies?
- What strategies and framework for advertising agencies to leverage AI in optimizing creative process that leads to value creation for clients?
- How can Prompt Engineer add value in optimizing current organizational productivity?

The research will take Dansa Kreatif as the research subject representing macro-level advertising agency in Indonesia which will propose two main outputs: first, a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) tailored with the concluded key attributes; and second, a strategic action plan using TOWS Analysis to in how to leverage AI to create direct value for agencies and their clients, focusing on cost-effectiveness and strategic AI investments. By implementing this PMS, advertising agencies can better manage the integration of AI into their creative processes, ensuring that the acceleration in content production does not compromise the creative integrity of the advertising industry.

Dansa Kreatif offers a comprehensive marketing services that can be seen on the workflow of the core process department at Dansa Kreatif in Indonesia. Which consists of dissecting the client’s brief until translating it into a consumer facing advertisements service as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Common Macro-Level Advertising Agency Operational Flow

In Figure 2, it can be concluded that the Account team initially collects client needs, setting the groundwork for all involved teams. The Strategic Planners then outline the campaign’s goals and methods based on market research. Then, the Creative team takes charge in creative ideation, concept crafting, until designing the campaign’s visual and copywriting, aligning them with the requirements for social media. Meanwhile, Production, whether in-house or external, generates the necessary campaign materials, paralleled by the Social Media Team crafting content and plans specific to each social platform. Meanwhile, the Social Media Team actively manages the digital campaign, interacting with the online audience. This study will focus on AI usage from Strategists and below.

II. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION: TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL

AI as a technology disruption, must consider the degree to which technology can perform a user's tasks is contingent on the degree to which individual abilities, task requirements and technology functionalities match (Marikyan & Papagiannidis, 2023). Therefore, the AI would effectively increase a company’s productivity only if balanced with well-educated and familiarized players, who aim to finish their daily tasks, as shown in the Figure 3 below.

Figure 3. The correlation of Employee Productivity and Campaign Performance

This Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) in Figure 3 represents the interaction between perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, having an effect on attitude, intention and use behavior (Davis, 1993; Davis, 1989). This research combines two Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) of AI as a tool in general and AI automation in the process of generating ad contents, as seen on Figure 4.

By adapting with the TAM framework, it's crucial to identify the relationship closely correlates with employee productivity that eventually connects with campaign performance.

Figure 4. Research Variable Conceptual Framework

Dissected from the variables in Figure 4, the key aspect visualized in black will act as the hypothesis variables. Their connections can be defined as a logically conjectured relationship between two or more variables expressed in the form of a testable statement (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

III. METHODS

A. Knowledge-Based Performance Management System

This research intends to develop a framework founded by Dermawan Wibisono on the Knowledge-Based Performance Management System (KBPMS). KBPMS simplifies the design of The Balanced Scorecard (BSC) approach, introduced by Kaplan and Norton in 1992, while incorporating the stakeholder-focused approach of the Performance Prism and the explicit performance indicators from the MBNQA/MBCfPE, aiming to offer a more holistic and stakeholder-inclusive performance management system (Fatima, Wibisono, & Adhiutama, 2019). This research adapts the KBPMS work in Figure 5 with the context of advertising industry. Therefore, the consolidated research framework and its key variables and the research methodology is visualized in Figure 5:

Figure 5. PMS development framework. (Source: Author)

Based on on Figure 5, the research will need specific information and data to acquire in each stage:

Stage 1: Acts as the initial phase of gathering fundamental data, three primary sets of information must be considered: (1) Company Environment Information, (2) Financial and Market Information, and (3) Product or Service Information. Therefore, this information will be gathered through a qualitative descriptive method from Dansa Kreatif's business report.

Stage 2: The Design Phase, with a mixed methodology between qualitative and quantitative will be conducted in order to identify and prioritize performance variables crucial for the advertising industry. Ensuring alignment with the organization's strategy, vision, mission, and objectives. In Fig. 3, the integration of the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) aimed to quantify and qualify linkages of those performance variables. Lastly, Benchmarking will be done to compare the existing PMS with the proposed PMS to identify the improvement done.

Stage 3: Due to the time and resource limitation, this research will focus on recommending the refreshment plan for this PMS from actionable timeline and tasks.

Samples are taken from two sample-ends: Advertising professionals (practitioners) and audience (consumers). The sampling method is a non-probability sampling: This dual-sided approach aims to gather insights from both sides to integrate and identify correlations between practitioners' reported productivity and audience response to creative outputs (creative performance).

B. Quantitative research

The research was distributed questionnaires to two sample groups to quantify their insights. The question types are structured questionnaires with Dichotomous scale and Numerical scale to ensure valid and tangible insights.

Sample Group A: Professionals at Agency X and audience on their AI integration level (based on the intensity of AI usage on a daily basis) and how it affects their productivity.

1. CREATIVE TEAM

- **Graphic Designers:** Image editing, layout creation, and automated design generation.
- **Copywriters:** Content generation, language enhancement, and grammar checks.
- **Art Directors/Creative Directors:** Concept ideation, trend analysis, and mood board creation.

2. IN-HOUSE PRODUCTION TEAM

- **Editor, Videographer, Producer:** Content editing, voice recording

3. STRATEGIC PLANNERS TEAM

- **Strategists/Planners/Analysts:** Market research, trend analysis, audience segmentation, and predictive modeling for campaign planning.

Sample Group B: Age-representative advertising consumers on their perception of AI-generated advertisement reference, Sourced from Statista (2023), We Are Social Indonesia (2023), and IDN Research Institute (2022)) which consists of:

1. MILLENNIALS

- **Size:** 89.7 million (34% of population)
- **Media:** Primarily digital - social media, mobile apps, video platforms, messaging apps.
- **Engagement:** Driven by social impact, user-generated content, and personalized experiences.
- **Media Consumption:**
 - 67% watch TV (average 2.5 hours daily)
 - 99% use the internet
 - 98% use smartphones

2. GENERATION Z

- **Size:** 69.5 million (26% of population)
- **Media:** Short-form video, social media, messaging apps.
- **Engagement:** Prioritize authenticity, diversity, and humor. Value quick information and visual content.

- **Media Consumption:**
 - 52% watch TV (average 2 hours daily)
 - 99% use the internet
 - 99% use smartphones

C. Qualitative research

In-depth Interviews (Qualitative): the interview will be conducted to Sample Group A, specifically managerial-level representatives at Dansa Kreatif on their perception toward AI-generated creative output and their judgment of the quality and creativity. The interview is a semi-constructed interview to ensure representative perception of creativity with a more open manner discussion while still maintaining the research objective with leading open-ended questions. Their insights will be used to support the hypothesis and variable prioritization.

D. Data Analysis Method: Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)

Through pairwise comparison, this research identifies the variables influencing the perspective of the Performance Management System (PMS) associated with the company's vision and mission. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is employed to assess the significance of relationships between indicators. In this research, AHP is specifically utilized to determine the weights of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The calculation of KPI weights is performed using AHP online, leveraging its effectiveness as a simple decision-making tool for complex, unstructured, and multi-attribute problems.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data and insights are processed throughThe Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) as a tool involving three primary steps: constructing hierarchies, computing weight factors, and establishing priorities.

A. Constructing Hierarchies

Through the Knowledge-Based Performance Management System (KBPMS), this proposal will modify its perspectives and aspects to align with the organizational realities in integrating AI and to streamline the connection between performance indicators and the overarching strategic goals. The variables on the right columns have been selected based on the acquired data (quantitative and qualitative), comprehensive literature reviews, and insights derived from the author’s expertise within the industry. This structure in Figure 7 becomes the foundation for the hierarchy criteria of variable importance.

Figure 6. Proposed Rationalization of Performance Indicators (Source: Author)

The rationalization in Figure 6 is adapted from the KPMBs variable categorization, Organizational Output and Business Results which act as the most immediate and measurable impact of AI integration within Dansa Kreatif Indonesia. AI-driven revenue growth and cost-saving efficiencies serve as tangible benchmarks for assessing the value AI brings to the company. Beneath this layer is the Internal Process, where AI’s contribution is the most visible as it highlights the organizational actual usage of AI tools on daily basis, which will be the focus on this proposal. At the foundational level, Resource Capability lies in the human capital development of AI tools

B. Pairwise Comparison

This proposal focuses on the Internal Process layer to propose the most effective performance management system for internal force in leveraging AI. This aligns with the pairwise comparisons start from Level 2 of the AHP (Wibisono, 2010). In this proposal within the Internal Process level, the factors are simplified into three are: Creative Process Improvement (C), Task Completion Efficiency (E), and Quality of Creative Output (Q) as seen on Figure 8.

Figure 7. Variable Linkage Between Layers

The categorization in Level 2 on Figure 8 were transferred directly from the process of gap analysis. This means that the AHP model decides on which one of these four factors (C, E, Q) should be in the priority of improvement to increase the company’s competitiveness in the Business Perspective.

C. List of criteria and sub criteria

Based on the subcategories for the three categories, through a structured Pairwise Comparison Method, it seeks to quantify and prioritize these factors and sub-factors crucial for making informed strategic decisions in the context of AI implementation in advertising agencies. The consolidated criteria and sub criteria can be seen in detail on Table 4.

Table 1. Criteria and Sub Criteria

Criteria	Sub-criteria	Definition
Creative Process Improvement	Creative Inspirations	How AI provides initial creative references able to inspire the creative team
	Originality	AI’s capability in producing new ideas that other campaigns/parties hasn’t done before within the same context
	Collaboration	AI as a platform for the team to collaborate personal takes on ideas

	Creative Morality	AI to produce socially acceptable ideas
Task Completion Efficiency	Prioritization Planning Process	AI as a tool to enhance employee’s time management by streamlining tasks
	Task attractiveness	AI in enhancing the enjoyment of doing tasks for employees
	Team commitment	AI’s attractiveness in making the employees learn about the tools
	Reduced working time	The time efficiency caused by AI automation
	Employee efficiency	The human skills that can be replaced by AI automation to reduce the numbers of employee needed
	Quantity of creative output	The number increase of contents that AI can produce compared to the conventional human-generated process
Quality of Creative Output	Visual quality	The aesthetic appeal and technical excellence of AI-generated ads
	Copywriting quality	The ability of AI to construct an engaging writing structure and vocab
	Campaign Message	The ability of AI to produce brand narration/story that evokes human emotion
	Production finesse	The tools that AI provide to maximize and enhance the production process
	Audience acceptance	The audience’s willingness to follow the ad’s direction (CTA)
	Value creation for clients	The brand awareness and sales caused by AI automation in producing the ads

Table 1 elaborates how each sub criteria has a direct impact on Dansa Kreatif’s business. The sub criteria under Creative Process Improvement is categorized based on how AI can enhance the creative performance of the employees. While the sub criteria under Task Completion Efficiency represents the effort and time efficiency caused by AI automation. While the sub criteria under Quality of Creative Output is focusing on the finesse of the end products and its impact to the audience.

D. Consolidated Results

Aside from the priorities of each the categories, the consolidated Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) results for Dansa Kreatif focuses on Value Creation for Clients, Audience Acceptance, and Production Finesse as the top priorities for AI investment strategy. The consolidated priority rank of all sub criteria can be seen on the diagram in Figure 9.

Figure 8. AHP Consolidated Result

As seen on the Figure 8, Value Creation for Clients (13.2%) is chosen as the top priority which raises the importance of AI to increase the precision of target marketing that led ads to acquire direct engagement and brand awareness for clients. This proves that AI integration should shift a part of its investment to directly contribute to client ROI from the current creative process-focused integration (Appendix. 1)

Audience Acceptance (13.0%) showed the importance of aligning AI-generated content with consumer expectations and preferences. This confirmed the urgency to improve the utilization of AI in creating better quality narrative, since the current capability is that audience still prefers human-generated narrative rather than AI (Appendix. 2). This strategy will require better prompt skill in generating a compelling story.

Production Finesse (11.3%) reflects the necessity to leverage content production AI tools, with Dansa Kreatif’s low integration in such tools (Appendix 3). Improving production finesse with AI aimed to lead to a leaner organization that Dansa is aiming for, since there will be fewer post-production needed and cost effective.

E. PMS Proposal

The consolidated result of the KPI weightage for the Internal Process with AI integration is detailed in Table 5 below.

Table 2. Proposed KPI Weightage

Criteria	Sub-criteria	Indicator	KPI Weight
Creative Process Improvement	Creative Inspirations	Number of AI-generated concepts used as a basis for campaigns.	0.443
	Originality	Percentage of AI-generated ideas that are unique compared to existing campaigns within the same timeframe.	0.244
	Collaboration	Number of collaborative sessions facilitated by AI platforms per project.	0.218

	Creative Morality	Compliance rate of AI-generated content with ethical advertising standards.	0.095
Task Completion Efficiency	Prioritization Planning Process	Reduction in time spent on task organization after AI integration.	0.073
	Task attractiveness	Employee satisfaction score regarding task engagement post-AI implementation.	0.073
	Team commitment	Training completion rate on AI tools among creative team members.	0.199
	Reduced working time	Average reduction in hours spent on routine tasks due to AI automation.	0.282
	Employee efficiency	Decrease in headcount or hours required for repetitive tasks, measured before and after AI integration.	0.227
	Quantity of creative output	Increase in number of campaigns or creative outputs produced per quarter post-AI.	0.146
Quality of Creative Output	Visual quality	Improvement in scores from client and peer reviews on the visual appeal of AI-generated ads.	0.089
	Copywriting quality	Enhancement in readability and engagement metrics of AI-written content, as measured by A/B testing.	0.072
	Campaign Message	Engagement metrics (likes, shares, comments) on narratives/story elements specifically generated by AI.	0.164
	Production finesse	Reduction in production errors and increase in process efficiency metrics post-AI tool integration.	0.203
	Audience acceptance	Conversion rates or follow-through actions on AI-driven campaigns' calls-to-action (CTA).	0.234
	Value creation for clients	Increment in client-reported brand awareness and sales metrics attributable to AI-driven campaigns.	0.237

The sub criteria weightage in Table 5 above is the final proposed KPIs for the Performance Management System. With the detailed weightage for each sub criteria, the evaluation scoring will be based on the prioritizing result represented by the managerial stakeholders of internal process.

V. CONCLUSION

For this research, the linkage strategy was selected based on the three most influential variables within the internal process as identified by AI integration experts. These variables were chosen because specialists determined they have the greatest impact on

outcomes. This methodical selection ensures that the analysis focuses on the most critical aspects of performance as influenced by AI technology. The effect between each variables is illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Linkage Scheme

From Figure 9, it can be summarized that the top 3 prioritization has a parallel effect that eventually leads to Cost Effectiveness and Client Retention. Production Finesse as the first step to enhance the value creation process by allocating more AI tools investments that are more resourceful and advanced. With the heightened quality and capacity of ad exposure, it is expected to drive a positive consumer perception toward the brands. Which is a major consideration for advertising agencies clients to keep a sustainable partnership. AI also enable cost effectiveness from the agency, and act as a distinctive value for clients.

VI. STRATEGIC BUSINESS SOLUTION

Dansa Kreatif best approaches the Maxi-Maxi strategy to leverage AI integration. The strategies for integrating AI into Dansa Kreatif's operations are centered on amplifying cost efficiency and technological capabilities to redefine service delivery and production processes. These approaches aim to provide both competitive pricing and enhanced operational effectiveness.

Strategy 1: Client Cost Re-evaluation: A re-assessment of Dansa Kreatif's pricing strategy is necessary to leverage AI's cost-efficiency benefits. By integrating AI tools that enhance operational efficiency, particularly in the creative department, Dansa Kreatif can offer services at a more competitive price. This strategy not only attracts new clients by offering greater value but also retains existing clients with cost-effective solutions. The reduction in manual labor through AI in creative processes can also free up employee time for more strategic tasks, thereby increasing overall productivity.

Strategy 2: AI-based Market Research Process: There is significant potential in expanding AI use beyond the creative department to include market research. By investing in advanced AI tools capable of generating in-depth market insights and accurate target demographics, Dansa can greatly enhance its strategic decision-making process. Tools such as IBM Watson and Google Cloud AI offer robust data analysis capabilities that can transform vast amounts of data into actionable insights, thus empowering strategists to tailor campaigns more effectively to the target audience.

Strategy 3: AI-driven Production House: Implementing AI-driven tools in the production process can streamline operations and reduce dependency on external resources. For instance, using AI for generating visual content can minimize the need for physical photoshoots, and AI voice synthesis tools like Descriptor Synthesia can replace traditional voice-over recording, significantly cutting down production costs and time. This shift not only enhances the efficiency of the production house but also allows for greater scalability of content creation, with potentially faster turnaround times for client campaigns.

VII. PROPOSED WORKFLOW: PROMPT ENGINEER

The proposed workflow for Dansa Kreatif integrates the intended Prompt Engineer to enhance specific segments of the internal process: strategic planning, creative development, and production. This reorganization aims to optimize operations by leveraging specialized expertise at critical points in the workflow. The introduction of Prompt Engineers is expected to refine workflow efficiency by distributing specific tasks according to the expertise of each engineer. Based on the In-Depth Interview with internal stakeholders, the role of each prompt engineer is best illustrated in Figure 10 below.

Figure 10. Proposed Workflow

Based on the new proposed workflow in Figure 11, integrating each of the Prompt Engineers is a strategic approach to hyper segmentize the prompting process in each internal core process. The detailed role of each Prompt Engineer is explained below:

A. Market Insights Prompt Engineer: The Market Insights Prompt Engineer specializes in using AI tools to gather and analyze market data, transforming it into actionable insights. This role is crucial for strategic planners, helping them refine audience targeting strategies. The Prompt Engineer facilitates the AI's synthesis of complex market trends and consumer behaviors to provide precise, data-driven insights, enhancing decision-making processes and ensuring that campaigns are aligned with market demands effectively.

B. Creative Prompt Engineer: The Creative Prompt Engineer uses advanced AI tools to generate initial creative prompts that serve as catalysts for the creative team. This role is essential for accelerating the creative process to significantly reduce the time required to move from concept to development. By effectively prompting AI, this engineer ensures the creatives receive a stream of relevant and innovative ideas and concepts that can be further developed into full-fledged designs and campaigns.

C. Production Prompt Engineer: The Production Prompt Engineer applies AI tools to optimize production processes within the Production House. This role is focused on enhancing the quality of the final outputs by using AI to automate and refine production steps, thus minimizing the need for manual refinements. The engineer ensures that AI-generated prompts lead to higher quality deliverables right from the production stage, reducing errors and improving efficiency.

Before engaging with a Prompt Engineer, each team is required to prepare a detailed brief. This ensures that the expectations are clearly set and aligned across all teams. Given that Prompt Engineers will receive task requests from multiple teams, Project managers will prioritize tasks based on urgency and strategic importance, ensuring that resources are allocated efficiently and that project timelines are met.

The proposed PMS framework focuses on identifying crucial attributes and prioritize them into a set of performance metrics for Dansa Kreatif to use for constant evaluation and consideration in AI-related investments for the future. The attributes with the most weightage in the performance metrics are: **Value Creation for Clients, Audience Acceptance, and Production Finesse**. The goal of this PMS is to create a sustainable cause effect value creation between all stakeholders as illustrated in Figure 12 below.

Figure 11. The Expected Sustainable Value Creation with the PMS Disruption

Source: Author

As illustrated in Figure 11, with the concluded prioritized variables from the perspective of the practitioners being Creativity, Innovation, and Execution, this PMS aims to enhance operation that results in time, quality, and productivity effectiveness. This is expected to optimize audience’s acceptance through increased ad quality in visual appeal, intriguing story, and emotional evocation.

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